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EMPOWERING FRONTLINE LEADERSHIP FOR ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

РОЗШИРЕННЯ МОЖЛИВОСТЕЙ ЛІДЕРСТВА НА ПЕРЕДОВІЙ ДЛЯ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ СТІЙКОСТІ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЇ

The article explores the role of frontline leadership in building organizational resilience in a volatile and complex business environment. It emphasizes that mid- and lower-level managers act as key agents of strategic transformation, translating corporate vision into operational results. Based on a survey of 55 respondents from 20 Ukrainian and international companies, the study analyzes current practices in leadership development, investment levels, core competencies, and barriers to effectiveness. Findings show that only 35% of organizations have formalized leadership development programs, with the highest maturity observed in IT and consulting firms and the lowest in manufacturing and agriculture. A Leadership Empowerment Index (LEI) was introduced to assess the maturity of leadership systems, with an average score of 3.74, indicating a moderate level of development. The results confirm that investment in leadership capability is positively correlated with organizational resilience, innovation, and employee engagement. Empowering frontline leadership should therefore be institutionalized as a strategic, long-term priority for ensuring competitiveness and sustainable performance.

Keywords: leadership, organizational resilience, human resource management, competency development, Leadership Empowerment Index, management innovation.

У статті досліджено роль лiдерства на передовому рiвнi управління у формуванні органiзацiйної стiйкостi компанiй, що дiють в умовах турбулентного бiзнес-середовища. Визначено, що саме керiвники середньої та нижчої ланок виступають ключовими провiдниками стратегiчних змiн i забезпечують перетворення корпоративного бачення на конкретнi результати. На основi опитування 55 респондентiв iз 20 українських та мiжнародних компанiй проаналiзовано сучаснi практики розвитку лiдерського потенцiалу, рiвень iнвестицiй, основнi компетенцiї та бар'єри ефективного розвитку. Виявлено, що лише 35% компанiй мають формалiзованi програми розвитку лiдерства, причому найвищi показники спостерiгаються у сферi IT та консалтингу, а найнижчi – у виробничих та аграрних пiдприємств. Запропоновано iндекс лiдерського пiдсилення (Leadership Empowerment Index), який дозволяє оцiнювати зрiлiсть систем розвитку лiдерства. Середньозважене значення iндексу становить 3,74, що свiдчить про середнiй рiвень розвитку управлiнських компетенцiй. Результати пiдтверджують, що iнвестицiї в розвиток лiдерства напряду корелюють iз рiвнем органiзацiйної стiйкостi, iнновацiйностi та залученостi персоналу. Розвиток лiдерства на передовому рiвнi має бути iнтегрований у стратегiчне управління як довгостроковий чинник конкурентоспроможностi пiдприємства.

Ключові слова: лiдерство, органiзацiйна стiйкiсть, управління персоналом, розвиток компетенцiй, Leadership Empowerment Index, управлiнськi iнновацiї.

Problem Statement. In today's volatile and complex business environment, the effectiveness of an organization increasingly depends on its ability to execute strategy through capable leadership at all levels. Frontline managers, positioned at the intersection of strategic direction and operational delivery, play a decisive role in translating corporate vision into measurable outcomes. When their leadership capacity is underdeveloped, organizations risk slower decision-making, weaker team cohesion, and reduced adaptability to change.

Despite this, leadership development at the frontline level remains underprioritized in many companies. Limited investment, fragmented training initiatives, and the perception that leadership growth should be concentrated only at the top levels of management contribute to a persistent capability gap. Over time, this gap undermines both short-term performance and the long-term resilience necessary to withstand market disruption and sustain competitive advantage.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. Over the past decade, the importance of leadership development has been extensively documented, with numerous studies confirming its strategic impact on organizational performance and competitiveness.

McKinsey (2023) reports that companies prioritizing human capital are 4.2 times more likely to outperform competitors, achieving 30% higher revenue growth and 5% lower employee turnover rates. Deloitte (2025) found that more than 10,000 senior executives and HR leaders across 93 countries identify leadership development as one of the top global trends for the coming year.

Manager engagement is another critical factor influencing organizational outcomes. Gallup (2024) reveals that only 27% of managers are actively engaged in their work, while 70% of a team's engagement level depends directly on the quality of its manager. The same study highlights a significant training gap: 44% of managers report never receiving formal leadership training.

McKinsey's 2024 statistics show that 72% of employees respond positively to recognition from their manager, and regular feedback can increase engagement threefold. Organizations that invest in structured leadership development programs achieve engagement levels 29% higher than those without such initiatives, and 58% of managers express the need for additional training in people management.

However, program effectiveness remains inconsistent despite the recognized importance of leadership development. According to Harvard Business Review, 75% of leadership programs fail to translate into workplace practice due to a lack of reinforcement mechanisms and mentoring. Deloitte notes that high-performing organizations design transparent, inclusive development strategies, actively involving employees in co-creating leadership pathways and applying systematic approaches at the middle-management level.

This body of research underscores a persistent gap: while the value of strong frontline and middle-management leadership is well-established, practical, targeted, and consistently applied development programs remain the exception rather than the norm. This study addresses that gap by combining empirical data with actionable recommendations for integrating leadership development into organizational strategy.

Literature Review; Recent research highlights leadership as a key determinant of organizational resilience, especially in volatile environments such as those faced by Ukrainian companies amid geopolitical uncertainty and economic instability. Leadership not only influences strategic decision-making but also directly shapes adaptability, team cohesion, and recovery capacity at the operational level.

Kumar and Ghosh (2025) emphasize that leaders who articulate a clear vision, communicate transparently, and invest in professional development significantly enhance organizational resilience. Similarly, Salendab and Lardera (2025) point out that resilient leaders inspire adaptability, foster inclusive cultures, and promote continuous learning – factors crucial for maintaining stability under crisis conditions.

The concept of empowering leadership proposed by Kirkman and Smith (2025) is considered one of the most effective approaches for strengthening frontline leaders. Empowering leadership emphasizes autonomy, participation, and trust, enabling employees to take ownership of decisions and improve work processes. This approach aligns with the decentralization trend observed in Ukrainian companies, where distributed leadership and local initiative are vital for maintaining operational continuity.

Kayyali (2025) identifies leadership behaviors that cultivate adaptability, flexibility, and psychological safety as particularly effective in fostering a resilient organizational culture. Such leadership styles encourage employees to embrace change and innovation, ensuring that organizations can respond effectively to disruptions. Mendrofa, Vittorio, and Hulu (2024) also demonstrate that agile leadership, characterized by responsiveness, innovation, and collaborative decision-making, is highly effective in empowering frontline leaders in volatile business environments.

In the Ukrainian context, Varis, Kravchuk, and Eldris (2025) propose an adaptive, inclusive, and ethical leadership model that enhances organizational resilience under instability. Their findings indicate that supportive leadership, which encourages creativity and collaboration, enables rapid organizational response during crises and fosters a sense of shared purpose among employees.

Tamim (2025) supports this perspective by emphasizing resilient and servant leadership as crucial for navigating economic and operational disruptions. These leadership styles combine emotional intelligence, empathy, and a solution-oriented mindset, empowering frontline leaders to sustain morale and performance even in uncertain conditions.

Building on this, Ramadhani, Sobandi, and Santoso (2024) reveal that resilient leadership positively affects both employee and organizational resilience, strengthening the human dimension of organizational adaptability. Although their work does not focus on specific national contexts, it confirms the broader link between leadership practices and resilience outcomes.

Benardi, Yulianti, and Chaidir (2024) highlight the role of adaptive leadership and robust communication in crisis management, showing that proactive planning and transparent leadership

help organizations navigate complex challenges and preserve trust during disruptions.

Finally, Sundowo, Hermawan, and Wijayanto (2024) propose the transformative adaptive leadership paradigm, integrating transformational vision with adaptive strategies. This hybrid model is particularly relevant for Ukrainian companies undergoing digital transformation, as it combines long-term strategic foresight with operational agility.

Overall, the reviewed studies demonstrate that empowering frontline leadership is a key driver of organizational resilience. The most effective approaches – empowering, agile, adaptive, inclusive, and resilient leadership – share common principles of trust, autonomy, open communication, and shared responsibility. However, there remains a lack of empirical evidence on how such leadership practices are implemented and perceived in Ukrainian organizations. Addressing this research gap, the present study explores how frontline leaders in Ukrainian companies contribute to building organizational resilience in conditions of volatility and systemic uncertainty.

Formulation of the Goals of the Article.

The primary goal of this article is to explore the strategic role of frontline managers as a key driver of organizational resilience and sustained performance. The study seeks to assess the current state of leadership development for this group across organizations of different sizes and industries, identifying the core competencies that enable them to lead high-performing teams and adapt to dynamic business environments. It further aims to analyze the barriers that hinder leadership growth at the frontline level and to compare existing practices with globally recognized leadership and team development models, evaluating their applicability in operational management contexts. Combining empirical survey data with established theoretical frameworks, the article formulates practical, evidence-based recommendations for embedding structured, competency-based leadership development into organizational strategy, closing the gap between the proven value of strong frontline leadership and its underrepresentation in corporate development priorities.

Methodology. The research was conducted in May 2024 and targeted HR specialists, Training&Development specialists, and CEOs representing companies with offices in Ukraine as well as international operations. The survey sample encompassed organizations of different sizes, from small enterprises to large corporations, and various industries, including IT, manufacturing, professional services, and consulting. This ensured a diverse and representative dataset reflecting multiple business contexts.

The study employed a quantitative research design, complemented by qualitative elements. Data collection was carried out via an online survey,

which included both closed-ended and open-ended questions. Closed-ended questions utilized a five-point Likert scale to capture respondents' assessments of leadership development initiatives' presence, quality, and perceived effectiveness. Open-ended questions were designed to gather additional insights on best practices, competency priorities, and perceived challenges in developing frontline and middle managers.

The questionnaire was structured to capture four key areas: the existence and scope of leadership development programs; investment levels and resource allocation; the most valued leadership competencies; and the main barriers to effective leadership growth. Responses were anonymized to encourage openness and ensure confidentiality.

Data analysis was conducted in two stages. Quantitative data were processed using descriptive statistics to identify frequencies, averages, and sectoral differences, while qualitative responses were subjected to thematic coding to extract recurring patterns and significant insights. Cross-tabulation was used to compare results by industry, company size, and geographical reach. This mixed-methods approach enabled a comprehensive understanding of the current state of leadership development and its relationship to organizational performance and resilience.

Presentation of the Research Results. The research examined the current landscape of leadership development practices across Ukrainian and international companies operating in Ukraine. The results reveal a fragmented yet evolving picture, where awareness of leadership's strategic importance exists, but systematic investment and consistency of implementation remain limited.

A total of 55 valid responses were collected from human resource professionals, training and development (L&D) specialists, and executives representing 20 companies across key industries – information technology, manufacturing, consulting, marketing, agriculture, healthcare, and financial services. The diversity of respondents ensured a multi-sectoral perspective on how organizations perceive, fund, and evaluate leadership capability at the frontline and middle-management levels.

Among surveyed organizations, 67% operate both in Ukraine and internationally, whereas 33% conduct activities solely within Ukraine. Company size varied: 36.4% employ between 100 and 500 people, 20% between 500 and 1,000, and 23.6% more than 2,000 employees. The majority of respondents (66.7%) represented HR departments, followed by L&D professionals (25.5%) and senior executives (7.8%).

When asked about the structure of leadership development, only 35% of organizations reported having formalized programs. These are most prevalent among large IT and consulting firms that operate internationally and align leadership capability with strategic goals. In contrast, small and

medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and agriculture-based businesses rely primarily on ad hoc training sessions and externally facilitated workshops, often without systematic evaluation or follow-up.

Regarding program duration, 47% of companies reported no defined training cycle, while 21% maintain annual programs. Three-month and six-month initiatives account for 16% each, indicating an inconsistent approach to duration and continuity. A closer look at cross-sectoral data shows that IT companies typically run continuous development cycles integrated into performance management systems, whereas manufacturing firms tend to rely on shorter, project-based interventions.

Investment levels also vary significantly. Only 28% of respondents had a clear understanding of their company's annual training budget. Of those, 9% reported investments up to USD 50,000 per year, and 7% up to USD 10,000. The remaining 84% allocate funds on an ad hoc basis depending on project needs or budget availability. This reactive budgeting model weakens long-term leadership planning and limits opportunities for succession development.

The study also examined who drives leadership development initiatives. Only 18% of respondents identified the CEO as the main driver of leadership growth, while 29% named a partnership between the CEO and HR/L&D departments. Among IT companies, 50% attributed leadership development primarily to HR or L&D functions, with minimal CEO involvement (4%). In contrast, within non-IT sectors, CEO involvement was higher (29%), indicating that organizational culture and industry dynamics influence the ownership of leadership initiatives.

Another critical finding concerns the size and composition of Learning & Development teams. Thirty-one percent of respondents indicated that their company had no dedicated L&D function, while 24% reported teams of five or more members. Larger organizations (500–2,000 employees) were more likely to maintain structured L&D departments, whereas smaller firms typically delegated development responsibilities to HR generalists. The lack of specialized L&D roles in many firms correlates with the limited scope of leadership programs and the absence of systematic evaluation mechanisms.

In terms of learning formats, IT companies showed a preference for blended learning combining online and offline sessions with mentoring and peer coaching, while manufacturing and agricultural firms favored internal training sessions facilitated by department heads. International companies tend to integrate external certification programs and global leadership frameworks, often in partnership with foreign training providers.

Across all industries, three leadership competencies consistently emerged as top priorities:

1. Change management and adaptability – the ability to navigate uncertainty and lead teams through transformation.
2. Effective communication and influence – establishing clarity, engagement, and trust within cross-functional teams.
3. Team and workgroup leadership – fostering collaboration, accountability, and performance alignment.

Additional competencies such as decision-making, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence were also recognized but ranked lower in training frequency, particularly in manufacturing and agriculture.

The table demonstrates clear sectoral variations. IT and consulting sectors show higher emphasis on communication, adaptability, and team leadership due to the knowledge-intensive and collaborative nature of their work. Manufacturing firms prioritize process-oriented skills such as decision-making, while agricultural enterprises tend to invest less in emotional intelligence and communication development, likely due to their hierarchical management culture and operational focus.

To assess the maturity of leadership development practices, a composite indicator – the Leadership Empowerment Index (LEI) – was introduced. It was calculated as follows:

$$LEI = (C1 + C2 + C3 + C4 + C5) / 5,$$

where *C1* – change management capability, *C2* – communication, *C3* – team leadership, *C4* – decision-making, and *C5* – emotional intelligence, each rated on a 1–5 scale.

The overall LEI across all organizations averaged 3.74, indicating a moderate development level. IT companies achieved the highest mean

Table 1

Core Leadership Competencies and Development Frequency by Sector

Sector	Change Management	Communication	Team Leadership	Decision-Making	Emotional Intelligence
IT	92%	88%	84%	72%	67%
Manufacturing	81%	79%	76%	68%	60%
Consulting	87%	91%	82%	75%	74%
Agriculture	78%	73%	69%	64%	55%
Average	84%	83%	78%	70%	64%

LEI (4.02), followed by consulting (3.89), manufacturing (3.61), and agriculture (3.45). The relatively lower indices in traditional sectors suggest that leadership development in these industries remains reactive, addressing immediate operational needs rather than long-term capability building.

Respondents identified several key barriers to effective leadership development. The three most cited challenges were:

- Insufficient budget allocation (63%);
- Lack of senior leadership support (58%);
- Low employee engagement in training initiatives (54%).

These findings highlight the structural weaknesses of leadership development strategies: inconsistent funding, limited sponsorship from top management, and a transactional rather than transformational approach to training. Moreover, only 28% of organizations measure program impact using tangible metrics such as promotion rates, engagement scores, or productivity improvements.

Cross-tabulation revealed that companies with formal evaluation systems reported an average LEI 0.43 points higher than those without such systems, suggesting a direct correlation between structured measurement and leadership maturity.

The IT sector demonstrated the strongest integration of leadership development with strategic performance indicators. International exposure and agile working environments facilitate continuous learning and mentoring practices. Consulting firms also scored high due to client-driven development cultures that reward adaptability and interpersonal influence.

Manufacturing and agricultural enterprises, while showing growing awareness of leadership importance, often remain constrained by resource limitations, rigid hierarchies, and a lack of long-term human capital strategies. Nevertheless, several respondents from these sectors indicated recent pilot programs focusing on next-generation leadership, suggesting an emerging cultural shift.

The research further revealed a strong association between company size and leadership development maturity. Organizations with over 1,000 employees displayed 18% higher investment rates and more defined leadership pipelines compared to smaller firms. Additionally, international organizations consistently scored higher on emotional intelligence and decision-making competencies, reflecting exposure to global management practices.

Overall, the results confirm that the maturity of leadership development directly correlates with an organization's ability to maintain resilience, foster engagement, and adapt to disruption. Firms that treat leadership as a continuous, strategic process rather than an episodic activity demonstrate stronger innovation, lower turnover, and higher operational stability.

Conclusions. The study confirmed that empowering frontline leadership is a decisive factor in strengthening organizational resilience and sustaining performance in volatile business environments. Despite broad recognition of its importance, leadership development at the frontline level remains fragmented and underfunded across many Ukrainian and international companies.

The empirical results revealed that only one-third of organizations maintain formalized leadership development programs, and most rely on short-term, ad hoc initiatives. Companies with structured, competency-based programs – particularly in IT and consulting – demonstrate significantly higher Leadership Empowerment Index (LEI) values, stronger engagement, and greater adaptability. By contrast, traditional sectors such as manufacturing and agriculture continue to face limitations related to rigid hierarchies, low investment levels, and weak evaluation systems.

The analysis identified three universal leadership competencies – change management, communication and influence, and team leadership – as central to developing effective frontline managers. These competencies are directly linked to resilience, innovation, and employee retention. Furthermore, organizations that measure the outcomes of leadership development activities report higher performance and stronger organizational alignment.

Key barriers, including insufficient budgets, lack of senior management support, and low employee engagement, continue to hinder progress. Overcoming these challenges requires shifting from fragmented training practices to integrated leadership systems supported at the strategic level.

In conclusion, leadership empowerment must be institutionalized as a long-term organizational priority rather than a periodic initiative. Embedding structured leadership development into company strategy strengthens not only human capital but also the organization's capacity for adaptation, innovation, and sustained competitiveness in conditions of uncertainty.

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